

THE ROLE OF STORYTELLING IN DEVELOPING YOUNG LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18710732>

Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of the storytelling method in developing oral communication skills of primary school students. The main goal of the study is to determine the impact of storytelling-based lessons on students' pronunciation, vocabulary, fluency, and communication skills. The article discusses the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the storytelling method based on the analysis of theoretical sources. The results of the study show that the storytelling approach increases students' speech activity, develops the ability to speak confidently, and creates a natural communicative environment.

Keywords: storytelling, speaking skills, young learners, communicative competence, primary education, vocabulary development, fluency.

Introduction. Today, teaching a foreign language from an early age is one of the priorities of the education system. Primary school students have the ability to quickly master the language, and it is especially important to use effective methods in developing oral speech skills. Speaking skill is the most complex, but also the most necessary component of the language learning process. It requires not only a wealth of vocabulary, but also correct pronunciation, grammatical structure and speech appropriate to the communicative situation [1:B,47].

The storytelling method is consistent with the natural learning mechanisms of children. Since young students are prone to figurative thinking, language material presented through stories is mastered faster and more effectively [2:B,21]. Therefore, this article analyzes the role of the storytelling method in the development of speaking skills.

Main part. Storytelling is recognized as an effective pedagogical tool for developing oral communication skills in primary school students. This method serves to teach language in a meaningful context, rather than on the basis of individual grammatical units. Young students absorb information more quickly through concrete images and events than abstract concepts. Therefore, story-based learning is consistent with their natural learning mechanisms. Research shows that language material presented in a meaningful context is more firmly stored in long-term memory [2:B,35].

Cameron, Lynne emphasize that emotional and visual factors play an important role in the language acquisition process of young students. During the storytelling process, new words and phrases are naturally repeated, which helps them enter the active vocabulary [2:B,41]. Repetitive language units are an important factor in increasing students' fluency.

One of the important aspects in the formation of oral speech is the active participation of the student. In the process of storytelling, students listen to the story, discuss it, answer questions and try to retell the story. This process improves their pronunciation and develops the ability to express their own thoughts independently. Harmer, Jeremy notes the need to create a natural communicative environment for the development of speaking skills [1:B,82]. Story-based lessons create just such an environment, because in them language is used as a real means of communication.

The use of role-playing games and dramatization elements in the process of storytelling increases the speech activity of students. The student seeks to freely express his thoughts by playing the role of the hero. This reduces the level of speaking anxiety and strengthens self-confidence. Wright, Andrew emphasize that stories develop imagination and creativity in children, encouraging them to engage in speech activity [3:B,22].

The storytelling method is also an important tool for increasing students' vocabulary. Words are learned contextually within the context of the story, which allows them to be used correctly in the communication process. Ellis, Gail and Brewster, Jean note that story-based lessons also have a positive effect on students' work on pronunciation and intonation [4:B,67]. Dialogues in the story text provide students with a natural speech model.

Another advantage of the storytelling method is that it involves students in active communication. Tasks such as independently continuing the end of the story or adding a new character to the story develop students' creative thinking. In this process, the student focuses not on constructing a grammatically perfect sentence, but on conveying the meaning. As a result, speech is formed naturally and fluently.

In general, storytelling provides a comprehensive approach to developing speaking skills. It expands vocabulary, improves pronunciation, increases fluency, and develops students' ability to express themselves freely. Therefore, the story-based method can be widely used as an effective and innovative approach in the primary education process.

Conclusion. The analysis shows that storytelling is an important pedagogical tool for developing speaking skills in primary school students. Story-based lessons increase students' vocabulary, improve pronunciation, develop fluency, and develop communication skills. The method also increases students' motivation and encourages them to speak with confidence. In the future, even more effective results can be achieved by integrating storytelling with digital technologies.

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